

A Study on Performance Evaluation of Life Insurance Corporation of India

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Abstract

The life insurance corporation of India plays an important role in providing insurance protection against death and old age on the one hand and accelerating the growth of our economy. Safety and security have become a major concern for everybody. India has considerably developed economically but a section of people still feel unsafe and insecure. Insurance have come up as very important financial services in most part of the world. Insurance is one of the important segments in the economy for its growth. LIC Company provides long term funds that are essential for the development of personnel. This company has witnessed many phases of working, there are days when private sector companies initially then became nationalised. The LIC of India is also seriously competing with other private companies. In a way private players are trying to capture the market features of the LIC of India, which was enjoying a monopoly position for a long period of time. In this study the performance is evaluated. LIC has a capacity of taking up all the customers and return a huge profit. Its success process is determined by the terms of service they provide and it remains as a trusted company to invest for a secured future.

**Keywords: Insurance, income and expenditure, financial services, Economic development.
JEL CLASSIFICATION: G22, G28**

Introduction

LIC plays an important role in the society. Insurance helps us by giving protection against the possible chances of generating uncertain losses. It helps personnel to get rid worries and miseries of losses or destruction of property and death. Life insurance is a contract between us and the life insurance company, which provides us death benefits during the contract term. Buying insurance is extremely useful if there is principal earning member in the family unfortunate premature demise, our family can remain financially secure because of the life that we have purchased to protect us, our family and our future. The primary function of life insurance is therefore protection of the family. Even the insurance is also seen as a tool to plan effectively for our future years.

The market offers insurance plans that not only cover our need but also same time it grows our wealth too. If we have dependants and financial responsibilities towards us, then we certainly in need of it. Having a family means dependant, which in turn means as financial commitments. Finance comes in different form as loans, children education, medical expenses etc. what would happen if a person loses his life or suddenly become disabled being insured in a situation like this is a necessity. When our life is insured we feel safe an secured future. Even after a person death the amount from insurance is useful for the family to build up their future. There are also many plans available today come with a savings element built into it. These policies are not only for financially independents future, and to have a comfortable retirement. Life was not designed to be risk free so LIC has made the future and also helps to reduce risk.

Review of Literature

Mishra, K.C. (2016)¹ in their article on “Protection Industry: Recipe for a Learning Organization” say that like some other industry, protection industry in India experiences one test repeatable a hundred times, that is the imperatives of a framework.

Balasubramanian, T.S. furthermore, Gupta, S.P. (2014)² in their book on “Protection Business Environment” clarify finally the worldwide and Indian pictures of Insurance frameworks. The effect of globalization furthermore progression on Insurance business environment is likewise examined diagnostically to have a reasonable comprehension of the difficulties confronted by the protection business.

Wadikar Ashok Laxaman (2014)³ in his theory on “Inventiveness in the Insurance Industries”, Ph.D. Proposition submitted to the Department of Management, University of Pune, 2001. Affirms a general feeling that creativity in each action alone principles and overwhelms the business. In any case, in the meantime, the common sense and monetary avocation of that creativity are additionally to be investigated.

Dan Segal Leonard N. Stern School of Business New York University (2016)⁴ “An Economic Current Scenario of Performance Evaluation of Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) of India Analysis of Life Insurance Company Expenses” has broken down the costs of the Life Insurance Companies.

Objectives of the Study

- To measure the performance of LIC of India.
- To examine the comparison between the income and expenditure of LIC
- To analyze the trend of income and expenses of LIC

Research Methodology

Data Collection

The present study covers auxiliary information. Information and data have been extricated from annual reports of LIC. The scientist has gathered five years balance sheet and profit and loss account of the examined unit. It is additionally upheld by differently distributed diaries, written works of LIC.

Period of Study

The period of study was from 2013-14 to 2017-2018 which is for five years

Scope of Study

The present study covers secondary data of Life Insurance Corporation of India.

Analysis and Interpretation

**Table 1 Performance of Income &Expenditure of LIC
(2013-2014 to 2017-2018)**

Years	Premium	%	Com	%	Op.exp	%	LOAN	%	P/L	%
2013-14	17973748	100	1654920	100	1890239	100	96252229	100	8808241	100
2014-15	18672181	189.97	1493331	90.23	2096378	110.90	10095120	106.4	64377540	730.8
2015-16	19126455	191.93	1523962	102.04	2141484	102.15	10411060	144.2	4291069	.6.665
2016-17	20044777	201.14	1621324	106.38	2740651	127.97	10227066	156.93	3272887	76.27
2017-18	21316848	211.31	1775252	109.49	2839971	103.62	10273237	249.49	2265952	69.23
CAGR	10.56%		20.04%		6.88%		22.06%		7.89%	

Source: Annual Report of LIC

Chart 1 Performance of Income &Expenditure of LIC

Interpretation

The above table shows the growth in a premium over the years and also major factor is determined. The financial year 2013-14 is used as the base year. The premium collected during the 2013 -14 was Rs. 17973748 and it increased in the year 2016-17 with the percentage of 201.14 and with CAGR of 10.56%

Commission has been showing an upward trend. The highest amount of commission was earned during the year 2017-18 with the percentage of 109.48 with a CAGR 20.04%

Operating expenses have been showing an increasing trend. The highest amount of operating expenses incurred by the company was in 2016-17 .The CAGR is 6.88%

Lending of loan has increased from the base year to current year with CAGR of 22.06% Profit earned in 2013-2014 is RS8808241. It has observed that there was a loss during the year 2015-2016 of RS 4291069 .The CAGR of profit is 7.89%

**Table 2 Correlation Analysis of Income & Expenses
(2013-14 to 2017-18)**

Variable	prem	Com	Op.exp	Loan	C&b	p/l
Premium	1					
Commision paid	-.437	1				
Op.exp	-.250	.594	1			
Loan	-.259	.205	-.598	1		
C&b	-.264	-.613	-.402	-.165	1	
p/l	-.264	-.613	-.402	-.165	1.000**	1

Source: Annual Report of LIC

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level(2-tailed)

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level(2-tailed)

Interpretation

From the above table, it is clear that the correlation coefficient between total income and expenditure vary year to year and exist a strong positive relationship between the two variables. The above table debits the premium and commission are continuously increasing and other variable show a fluctuating trend. Lending of loan is a much higher percentage of income in the form of interest. Operating expenses shows a decline from the base year. The other variables show a random growth and decline respectively.

Relationship between Total Income and Expenditure

**Table 3 Total Income and Expenses of LIC
(2013-14 to 2017-18)**

Year	Total Income	Total Expenses
2013-2014	3,989.34	1494.76
2014-2015	4,452.45	1,956.19
2015-2016	5,085.17	2599.08
2016-2017	6980.61	3201.93
2017-2018	8,393.56	4092.44

Source: Annual Report of LIC

**Chart 2 Total Income and Expenses of LIC
2013-14 to 2017-18.**

The above figure shows the direction of total income and expenses of LIC for the study period

Interpretation

The above table concludes that there is rapid increase in the total income compare to the total expenses of the company.

Limitations of Study

- This study is restricted to Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) of India only.
- It is based on secondary data due to the nature of the study.
- The information used for the study is of only five years.

Suggestion

- The LIC has to make efforts to reduce their operating cost which is been constantly increasing over the years.
- The company has to make efforts to increase their premium which has been fluctuating from year to year.
- A comparative study of performance between LIC and other companies may help in narrow growth.
- As private insurance companies capture the market now a day, therefore, LIC should launch plans with more facilities.

Conclusion

LIC has wide market since the concept of life insurance is gaining a lot of significance in India. The Indian life insurance has reported strong growth in the past decade, mainly benefitting from low degree of insurance penetration in the country. The performance of LIC has been constantly good over the years. LIC being one of the significant players in Indian economy has to achieve effective results and ensure good performance. “The woods are lovely dark and deep, but LIC has to keep its promises and there are miles to go before it sleeps.

References

- Agarwalala, A.N., Life Insurance in India - A Historical and Analytical Study, 1961.
Bhole, LM, Financial institutions & Markets, Tata Mc Graw- Hill Limited, new Delhi.
www.irda.org
www.lic.com
www.banknetindia.com